

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

“Man Malalaman” kitobi haqida

S.A. Khashimova

DSc, dotsent

sabohat15@mail.ru

Kalit soʻzlar: qochqinlar, mentalitet, axloq, oʻzini oʻzi anglash.

Annotatsiya: ushbu tezisda "Men Malalaman" kitobi haqida boʻlib, unda butun dunyoni larzaga solgan 17 yoshli qizning oʻziga xos avtobiografik hayot hijoyasi bayon etiladi.

ABOUT THE BOOK "I AM MALALA"

Key words: refugees, mentality, morals, self-realization.

Abstract: this thesis provides a brief overview of the book "I am Malala", a kind of autobiography of a 17-year-old girl, whose unique story shocked the whole world.

О КНИГЕ «Я - МАЛАЛА»

Ключевые слова: беженцы, менталитет, нравы, самореализация.

Аннотация: в данном тезисе даётся краткий обзор о книге «Я - Малала», своеобразная автобиография 17-летней девушки, уникальная история которой потрясла весь мир.

A wonderful book about a teenage girl who was born and raised in a Pashto family. Autobiography of a 17 year old girl. A unique story of courage that shocked the whole world. Thanks to the excellent upbringing of her father, Malala was able to get an education at school, unlike most girls in Pakistan, she fought for the right of girls to get an education and be able to fulfill themselves in their country. For which she was wounded by militants. Unconscious, she was transported to Birmingham, where she continued her studies. Such a change in her life allowed her to take a fresh look at the education system in Pakistan. Subsequently, she created a fund to them. Mom and traveled to many countries to

help girls and children gain access to education. The book tells about the history of India and Pakistan, the way of life of families, customs and traditions. She writes a lot about her family, about the nature and environment that she had to leave. In addition, Malala describes the pain she experienced when she saw Syrian refugees, children who are forced to leave their studies and earn their family's bread. The book contains color photographs of her family and the events that changed her life.

An ordinary Pakistani girl was sentenced to death by the Taliban, but miraculously survived and escaped. She is fighting for the right to education in Pakistan. The book takes us to another corner of the world - Pakistan. The main character tells not only about herself. To make it clearer to the reader, the author decided to write the truth about the mentality and customs of the Pakistani people. The girl shares her experiences and fears, tells about the history of her country, tells the customs and lives of ordinary people. It plays an important role in the book. Two-thirds of the book is devoted to events and traditions and history. They serve as an addition to the autobiography and allow the reader to see the world through the eyes of a small child. The main character's name is Malala. She was born in the Swat Valley. The girl willingly shares with readers memories of her childhood and adolescence. Malala treats her father with great respect and honors her mother. He talks a lot about his family, about his beloved native land, about his ancestors. Already in childhood, our heroine has to make difficult decisions. From chapter to chapter we watch our little girl grow up. At the very end of the autobiography, we find out which path she chooses for herself.

The main idea of the book is to convey the truth to its readers. The circulation of the book diverges in all corners of the world. Including the book is translated and printed in our country. Completely without fear, the girl talks about a series of terrorist attacks and the invasion of the Taliban into their state. This book was not written to condemn or accuse anyone. The author wants to show how hard life is for people after trying to introduce Islamic laws into the country: "It turns out that I prevented the implementation of Islamic laws, and therefore they

decided to destroy me.” Malala was shot while she was traveling to school by bus. On that fateful day, two more girls were wounded.

One of Pakistan's problems is education. More precisely, its absence. Few children manage to complete primary school, let alone complete it. Malala and her father are actively involved in ensuring that the children from the Swat Valley receive a decent education. Malala describes the difficulties that every child who attends classes faces. What a labor it takes for young people to finish school and find themselves in this world! You can learn a lot from the book. You can learn about the difficult female burden. About what responsibilities women assumed, what problems they faced in front of society. About big and small events in Pakistan. How the country experienced the Taliban invasion, how the authorities reacted to the threat. How they restored the native land of Malala, and what happened next.

Malala's story makes you plunge headlong into places where war is raging. Somewhere you involuntarily think, somewhere you empathize. But there are things in the book that make you cry. Malala's autobiography will not leave anyone indifferent. The heroine herself appears before readers not only as an eyewitness, but also as an activist in the struggle for education. It's not as easy as it seems. The little girl is trying to do something and prove by her own example that everyone has a chance. “I am Malala. The world I live in has changed, but I have remained the same.” I would recommend this book to today's teenagers as a must-read.